

Environmental niche divergence of species from *Merodon ruficornis* group (Diptera: Syrphidae)

Jelena Ačanski^{1,*}, Marija Miličić², Laura Likov², Dubravka Milić², Snežana Radenković² and Ante Vujić²

¹ *BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Dr. Zorana Đinđića 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

² *Department of Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

*Corresponding author: acanskijelena@gmail.com

Received: March 3, 2016; Revised: April 8, 2016; Accepted: May 10, 2016; Published online: October 17, 2016

Abstract: In this paper we analyzed environmental differentiation of closely related species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group. By applying principal component analysis (PCA) and environmental niche modelling (ENM)-based techniques, we estimated the level of niche divergence of closely related species. Our results indicate that ecology has an important role in the diversification process in related species from the *M. ruficornis* group. Distribution patterns of all analyzed species are mainly affected by the limiting effects of the temperature of the coldest quarter and month, as well as by the precipitation of the wettest and driest quarters. Our results demonstrated that among all related species, with the exception of *M. ovaloides*, overall or partial divergence in environmental space is present. Importantly, the results indicate that the environmental niches of all endemic species are restricted to smaller parts of the environmental space. In the case of niche overlap, the niches of endemic species are placed along the border of the realized niche of the widespread related species. For species in which distribution is not limited by geographical barriers, environmental preferences could be considered as limiting factors for further expansion, as in the case of *M. alexandri*, a lowland species with very strict climatic adaptations. Knowledge about the environmental factors that might influence the diversification process can provide an explanation for the high diversity in other *Merodon* species groups.

Key words: environmental niche; PCA; MAXENT; ENMTools; *Merodon ruficornis* group

INTRODUCTION

Insects are sensitive to environmental changes and respond to all climatic oscillations within their niches. When insect species are confronted with severe environmental changes (e.g. large-scale climatic changes in geological history), they have three possible solutions: evolve, change range or become extinct [1]. There are a large number of examples showing insect species that have changed range and/or evolved as a response to repeated isolation during glaciation-interglaciation cycles [2-7]. In the Western Palearctic, there are multiple glacial refugia: southern Europe (Iberian, Apennine and Balkan peninsulas), the Anatolian Peninsula and southern Caucasus [2,8,9]. Fossil remains of different animal and plant species provide a clear picture that during the last ice age organisms with the northern and central European distribution survived in southern refuges beside the Mediterranean Sea [2], on the Iberian, Apennine and Balkan

peninsulas, and perhaps some near the Caucasus and Caspian Sea [10].

The genus *Merodon* Meigen (Diptera: Syrphidae: Merodontini) is comprised of more than 170 species and is the largest hoverfly genus in Europe [11,12]. Species from this genus are connected with bulb-forming plants which they use as food sources for the larvae [13-15], and as a result some are considered as pests [16]. This genus is distributed over the Palearctic and Ethiopian regions [17] and the Balkan and Anatolian peninsulas, which represent the main centers of biodiversity with a large number of local endemic species on islands, mountains or other isolated areas [11,12,18]. Species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group have been the subject of several integrated studies [17,19,20-23]. In the last decade, several new species from this group were described [18,20-23]. Recently, this monophyletic group was revised and identification key and distributional data for a total of

18 species were provided. According to the diagnosis given in Vujić et al. [21], species within the *Merodon ruficornis* group can be divided into several clusters of morphologically closest species. The distribution pattern of each cluster is similar, comprising of one widely distributed species and another sister species with a restricted range. A speciation process has taken place in these geographically isolated populations and has resulted in the formation of closely related species in different parts of the range of the common ancestor, as hypothesized by Vujić et al. [21].

Analyses of niche relationships among closely related taxa can provide insights into the ecological distinctiveness and mechanisms responsible for the diversification [24-27].

A species' fundamental niche consists of the set of all conditions that allow for its long-term survival, whereas its realized niche is that subset of the fundamental niche that it actually occupies. By definition, then, environmental conditions at the occurrence localities constitute samples from the realized niche. Analysis of species occurrences enables an approximation of the species' realized niche, in the study area and environmental dimensions being considered [28]. Here we used principal component analysis (PCA) and ecological niche modelling (ENM)-based techniques to examine the mechanisms of ecological divergence among closely related species within the *Merodon ruficornis* group.

PCA of environmental parameters is a method widely used in studying niche determination and differentiation. It allows comparison of environmental niches among investigated taxa to determine if they differ and if they do, to what degree. Additionally, it can isolate environmental parameters correlated with speciation [29] and can contribute to investigation of the environmental limits of taxa, suitable environments for protected or invasive species and species delimitation [7,30-38].

Species distribution models (SDMs) are increasingly being used to address a diverse range of applied and theoretical questions [39-41]. Also known as ecological niche models and bioclimatic envelopes, SDMs are correlative models that use environmental and/or geographic information to explain observed patterns of species occurrences [42].

The aim of this paper was to i) define the environmental envelope for each investigated species based on distributional, climate and elevation data; ii) quantify and compare environmental niches among related species using three different approaches; iii) establish abiotic factors that influence species range, and iv) identify factors that can correlate with speciation. Results obtained in this paper can contribute to understanding the speciation process in related species and also can explain why the Mediterranean basin is a hotspot for particular hoverfly genera.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Clusters of morphologically closest species

Environmental preferences were identified and compared among morphologically related species that are aggregated into four clusters based on morphological characters according to Vujić et al. [21]. Every cluster follows the same pattern of distribution that is characterized by one widely distributed and two endemic species with a narrow range.

The first cluster of morphologically close species contained *Merodon ruficornis* Meigen, 1822, *Merodon abruzzensis* van der Goot, 1969 and *Merodon lamellatus* Vujić & Radenković, 2012. *Merodon ruficornis* is predominantly distributed in central parts of Europe, including France to the west and the Apennine and Balkan peninsulas to the south. *Merodon abruzzensis* is locally endemic with a range on the Abruzzo Mountains in Italy, at the border of *M. ruficornis* distribution, while *M. lamellatus* is an endemic species from the Turkish part of the Caucasian region.

The second cluster consisted of the widely distributed European species *Merodon auripes* Sack, 1913, and two endemics: *Merodon alexandri* Popov, 2010 (Ukraine and Russian steppes) and *Merodon ponticus* Vujić & Radenković, 2012 (Caucasus Mountains).

The third cluster was composed of three morphologically related species, *Merodon trebevicensis* Strobl, 1900, *Merodon gallicus* Vujić & Radenković, 2012 and *Merodon hoplitis* Hurkmans, 2012. *Merodon trebevicensis* is a widely distributed species from the Alps in the west, to Crimea and central Turkey in the east.

Merodon gallicus is endemic for France and separated from *M. trebevicensis* by the Alps, while *M. hoplitis* is endemic to the Dinaric Mountains.

Cluster number four was comprised of three species: *Merodon loewi* van der Goot, 1964, *Merodon ovaloides* Vujić & Radenković, 2012 and *Merodon turcicus* Vujić & Hayat, 2012. *Merodon loewi* is a species with a wide range, from the Apennine Peninsula to Caucasus and Russian steppes. *Merodon ovaloides* is endemic for Kastamonu Province (Turkey), while the distribution of *Merodon turcicus* is restricted to south Caucasus.

Species occurrence data

In total, 1401 records representing 12 species from the four clusters of morphologically similar species were analyzed. Occurrence records were sampled from central and southern Europe, the Anatolian Peninsula and the Black Sea Region. Specimens were obtained from most of the European museums and private collections listed below: Benediktinerstift Admont, Austria; Croatian Natural History Museum, Zagreb, Croatia; Macedonian Museum of Natural History, Skopje, FYR Macedonia; Musée National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; Museo Zoologico La Specola, Firenze, Italy; National Museum, Prague, Czech Republic; Natural History Museum, London, UK; Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands; Naturhistorisches Museum Wien, Austria; Prirodnjački muzej Beograd, Srbija; Tel Aviv University, Israel; Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kiev, Ukraine; World Museum Liverpool, UK; Zemaljski Muzej Sarajevo, Bosnia- Hercegovina; Zoological Museum of The Finnish Museum of Natural History, Helsinki, Finland; Zoological Museum of Tulcea, Romania; Zoological Museum, Natural History Museum of Denmark, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark; Zoologisches Museum of the Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany; Entomological Museum of Isparta (EMIT); Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia and private collections of Axel Ssymank collection, Germany; Dieter Doczkal collection, Germany; Grigory Popov collection, Ukraine; Jeroen van Stenis collection, The Netherlands; John Smit collection, The Netherlands; M. J. Smart collection, UK; and Süleyman Sarıbiyik collection, Turkey.

Data preparation

Only records with precise distributional data were used. Localities with geographic coordinates were used without modification. Records without geographic coordinates were georeferenced and visually checked using Google Earth (Google Inc, California, USA, <https://www.google.com/earth>; accessed on Feb 10, 2015) based on detailed locality information. Localities with unclear information were removed from the data set.

Environmental data extraction

Nineteen bioclimatic variables and elevation data for each location were generated on the basis of WorldClim dataset [43] in 2.5 arc-minutes resolution using DivaGis software (DIVA-GIS version 7.5). The bioclimatic variables were derived from the monthly temperature and rainfall values in order to generate more biologically meaningful variables. They represent annual seasonality trends of temperature and precipitation, and extreme or limiting environmental factors. Distribution and richness maps were created in DivaGis.

Point based analysis of environmental variables

PCA was used to define the climatic profiles of the investigated species and to evaluate whether morphologically close species were separating along certain environmental factors. PCA was carried out applying a normal varimax rotation of factor loadings. Only factors with an eigenvalue greater than 1 were considered significant. Climate variables with a factor loading greater than ± 0.8 were interpreted as meaningfully correlated with the factor. A scatter plot of PCA score values was used to graphically display the position of the analyzed species in environmental space. ANOVA was carried out to determine overall differences in the derived factor scores between species. Significant difference in factor scores between species pairs was tested using Fisher's LSD post hoc. Indication of the adaptability of species for each PC was represented as standard deviation of factor scores. All statistical analyses were computed in Statistica® for Windows (version 12, Statsoft Inc, Tulsa, OK).

Ecological niche modelling

Niche projections were conducted using MAXENT (version 3.3.3), which is one of the most commonly used algorithms for species distribution modelling [39,44-48]. The maximum entropy (MAXENT) model [44] originates from the statistical mechanics [49]. The idea of MAXENT is to estimate the target distribution by finding the distribution of maximum entropy (i.e., that is closest to uniform) [39] by using occurrence records of the species and environmental variables. To eliminate highly correlated variables, we used VIF (variance inflation factor) analysis integrated in the package usdm (R package, version 1.1-15) in R platform (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria), which resulted in different combinations of Bioclim variables for every species used for modelling procedures. 70% of data were used for training the model, and 30% were used as test data. Equal weight was given to training sensitivity and specificity. Accuracy of the model was assessed using the AUC (area under the receiver-operator curve) value, which is one of the most commonly used measures of model performance [45]. Values of AUC ranged from 0.5 for models with no predictive ability, to 1.0 for models giving perfect predictions [50].

Tests of niche overlap

Niche overlap, identity and similarity tests for each species were calculated using ENMTools [51,52]. Niche overlap analyses (ranging from 0 – no overlap to 1 – complete overlap) were applied within each cluster of species using Schoener's D index [53]. The niche identity test was used to determine whether the ENMs generated for the species pairs in each cluster were identical or exhibited statistically significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$, $p \leq 0.01$). We compared the niche overlap value (D) of pairs of *Merodon* species to a null distribution, with an overlap value=100. The null hypothesis of niche identity was rejected when the empirically value for D was significantly distinct from the value expected from the pseudoreplicated datasets [52]. The identity test is conservative as it only assesses if the pair of species tolerates the exact same set of environmental conditions and it does not consider the surrounding space. For this reason, we also used the niche similarity test to evaluate if the examined species were more or less similar than expected

Fig. 1. Diversity of species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group. **A** – distribution; **B** – richness. The darker areas indicate highest richness (value range 1-5).

by chance, based on the environmental differences in their ranges [51,52]. The null hypothesis of niche similarity was rejected if the true measured overlap values were significantly lower (or higher) than the values generated by the background test. This test is conducted in both directions, and different directions may yield different results.

RESULTS

In this paper, diversity studies (species richness and altitudinal zonation) of the *M. ruficornis* group were analyzed, and for each cluster, environmental niche divergences were measured using three different approaches: i) point based analysis (PCA), ii) niche projections (MAXENT) and iii) niche overlap, identity and similarity tests (ENMTools).

The distribution of species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group encompasses Western Palearctic, without representatives on the Iberian Peninsula and northern Africa (Fig. 1A). The species altitudinal

Fig. 2. Results of altitude analysis of species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group. **A** – variability plot of species altitudinal gradient; **B** – relation between altitude and species richness.

range was from sea level to approximately 3000 m a.s.l. (Fig. 2A). Widely distributed species, such as *M. auripes*, *M. loewi*, *M. ruficornis* and *M. trebevicensis*, reside in areas at different altitudes. Endemics and species with a narrow range had smaller altitudinal ranges and were connected with mountain areas, all except *M. alexandri* and *M. gallicus*, which are lowland species (Fig. 2A). The relation between altitude and species richness is depicted in Fig. 2B. The highest number of species can be found at altitudes from 1000 to 2000 m. The species richness and diversity map show that the Balkan Peninsula is the main hot spot for this species group, and together with Anatolian Peninsula represent the biodiversity center of the *M. ruficornis* group (Fig. 1B).

1st cluster of morphologically close species

Merodon ruficornis has a wide altitudinal range (0-2000 m a.s.l.), unlike *M. abruzzensis* and *M. lamellatus*, which have considerably smaller altitudinal ranges, connected with mountain habitats. According to the available data, *M. abruzzensis* occurs at 1000-2000 m, while *M. lamellatus* has a slightly lower altitudinal range, but inhabits higher altitudes, from 1800 to 2500 m a.s.l. (Fig. 2A).

To identify the specific climate variables that best explain the geographic ranges occupied by each species, PCA analysis was used. PCA extracted five environmental dimensions (principal components), which together explained 96% of the variance. Overall significant separation among species occurs along

all five PCs (ANOVA: PC1: $F_{2,201}=30.95$, $p<0.00000$; PC2: $F_{2,201}=147.39$, $p<0.00000$; PC3: $F_{2,201}=13.22$, $p<0.000004$; PC4: $F_{2,201}=9.40$; $p<0.000125$; PC5: $F_{2,201}=31.20$; $p<0.00000$). The first principal component explains 50% of total variation, and is negatively correlated with altitude data and positively correlated with temperature (Bio1, Bio6, Bio11). Environmental variability connected with temperature variables is explained by PC1, PC2 and PC4, while precipitation was connected to PC3 and PC5. PC1 depicted a gradient for temperature of the coldest quarter and month, but an opposite gradient for the altitude value (Fig. 3A). The second PC was related to the mean diurnal range (Bio2) and isothermality (Bio3), explaining 17% of the total environmental variation. Additionally, PC4 illustrated the temperature gradient in the driest and the wettest quarter with 11% of the total variation (Fig. 3B). PC3 (13%) and PC5 (6%) elucidate precipitation in the wettest quarter and month, and precipitation seasonality, respectively (Table S1). Scatter plots showed species environmental niches and a clear separation of *M. lamellatus* and partial overlap of *M. ruficornis* and *M. abruzzensis* niches (Fig. 3). In order to confirm that there were substantial environmental differences among species pairs, the Fisher LSD test was conducted. Results showed that PC1 and PC2 differentiated all three species ($p<0.05$). Additionally, *M. abruzzensis* and *M. lamellatus* differ from *M. ruficornis* in PC3 and PC4, while *M. lamellatus* differs from *M. abruzzensis* and *M. ruficornis* in PC5. The climatic adaptability of each species was calculated as standard deviation around the centroids

Fig. 3. Distribution of species from cluster 1 in environmental space. **A** – temperature and altitude related axes (PC1 and PC2); **B** – temperature and precipitation related axes (PC3 and PC4).

Fig. 4. Niche projections based on Maxent for: **A** – *M. ruficornis*; **B** – *M. auripes*; **C** – *M. trebevicensis*; **D** – *M. loewi*. Colors represent different percentages of potential species distribution; spots represent current data of species.

of the PCs (Table S2). Standard deviation for PC1 showed that all three species have relatively similar adaptability to temperature and altitudinal changes. The high value for PC2 revealed a broad adaptability of *M. abruzzensis* to monthly and daily temperature ranges, unlike *M. lamellatus*. *Merodon ruficornis* had a higher adaptability related to temperature in the driest and wettest quarter and precipitation, reflecting its wide distribution (Table S2).

The predicted distribution of *M. ruficornis* showed that the most suitable environment with a probability of occurrence above 70% is in the Dinaric mountain range, but also in the part of the Alps between Italy, France and Switzerland, in the high parts of the Apennines in Italy and on the mountains in Turkey, Georgia and Russia along the coastal zone of the Black Sea.

50-70% of probability was in the Dinaric Mountains at lower altitudes, the lower slopes of the Apennines, central France, central and southern Germany and the lower slopes of the mountains around the Black Sea. Distribution of *M. lamellatus* is completely separated from the predicted distributions of *M. ruficornis*, while *M. abruzzensis* is distributed in the area where the model showed a 50% possibility of occurrence for *M. ruficornis*, indicating that the ecological niches of these two species are more similar (Fig. 4A).

Based on ENM, niche overlap is higher between *M. ruficornis* and *M. abruzzensis* ($D=0.442$) than between *M. abruzzensis* and *M. lamellatus* ($D=0.100$) and between *M. ruficornis* and *M. lamellatus* ($D=0.162$) (Table S3). According to the identity test, the null hypothesis of niche identity is rejected, mean-

Fig. 5. Distribution of species from cluster 2 in environmental space. **A** – precipitation and temperature related axes (PC1 and PC2); **B** – temperature related axes (PC1 and PC3).

ing that the climate envelopes of all pairwise comparisons of *Merodon* species are highly significantly more different than expected to randomly occur (Table S3). On the other hand, in the analysis of niche similarity, the null hypothesis is not rejected in all pairs of species. The environmental niches of *M. ruficornis* and *M. abruzzensis* were not statistically different ($p \geq 0.05$), presenting 44% of geographic overlap. The ecological niche of *M. abruzzensis* was less similar than expected by chance to that of *M. lamellatus* in both directions (Table S3). Other pairs of *Merodon* taxa shared niches that were more similar than expected by chance, but only in one direction (*M. lamellatus* with *M. ruficornis*) and not *vice versa*.

2nd cluster of morphologically close species

Merodon auripes is a species with a mostly continental distribution and wide altitudinal range (Fig. 2A). Based on the available material, *M. alexandri* is a lowland species, while *M. ponticus* is a high mountain species (Fig. 2A).

The environmental niches of species from the investigated cluster differed in four dimensions (PC1-PC4) and altogether explained 91% of the variability. The results of ANOVA showed that environmental preferences varied significantly across species in three PCs (PC1: $F_{2,145} = 38.77801$, $p < 0.00000$; PC2: $F_{2,145} = 222.2665$, $p < 0.00000$; PC3: $F_{2,145} = 16.84435$, $p < 0.00000$; PC4: $F_{2,145} = 0.246920$, $p < 0.781531$). Niche axis 1 (PC1) allowed a clear distinction between all three species. PC1 depicted a gradient of precipitation levels

of the driest quarter and month and annual precipitation, and explained 46% of the total variation (Fig. 5A). PC2 and PC3 were connected to temperature variables and explained 24% and 14% of variability, respectively. PC2 separated the lowland species *M. alexandri* from *M. auripes* and *M. ponticus* according to the mean temperature in the coldest quarter and month (Fig. 5A). PC3 clearly separated *M. ponticus* from *M. alexandri* and *M. auripes* based on altitude and mean temperature of the warmest quarter and month (Fig. 5B). Fisher's LSD test showed that PC1 differentiated all three species, while PC2 significantly separated *M. alexandri* from *M. ponticus* and *M. auripes*, and PC3 separated *M. ponticus* from *M. auripes* and *M. alexandri* ($p < 0.05$). These environmental distinctions across environmental axes are visible on a scatter plot (Fig. 5).

Merodon alexandri and *M. ponticus* have low deviations for each PC, reflecting their narrow geographic distributions and very strict climatic adaptations, especially for *M. alexandri* (Table S2). *Merodon auripes* had a wide adaptability to climatic fluctuations in the driest and warmer quarters (PC1, PC3), and the lowest values for temperature fluctuations in the coldest quarters. Based on niche projection, the highest probability of occurrence (70-100%) for *M. auripes* was along the coastal zone of the Black Sea, on the Carpatho-Balkan mountain belt, Dinaric mountain range, the Apennines and in the mountain area between Czech Republic, Germany and Austria. A probability between of 50-70% was found in the regions that border the areas with the highest percent-

Fig. 6. Distribution of species from cluster 3 in environmental space. **A** – temperature related axes (PC1 and PC4); **B** – precipitation related axes (PC2 and PC3).

age of suitability, and have lower altitudes compared with them. The potential distribution of *M. auripes* is clearly separated from the distribution of *M. alexandri* and *M. ponticus* (Fig. 4B).

In the second cluster, the niche overlap between the investigated *Merodon* species had generally low levels, from 0.177 for *M. auripes*-*M. alexandri* to 0.329 for *M. auripes*-*M. ponticus* (Table S3). Randomization tests of niche identity indicated that the species in each pair were more different than expected, so they are not ecologically equivalent ($p \leq 0.01$). The niche similarity was less pronounced than expected by chance in both directions for the pair *M. alexandri* and *M. ponticus*. For some pairs of *Merodon* species, niche similarity was greater than expected by random also in both directions, such as *M. auripes* with *M. alexandri* (Table S3). No significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) were recorded between *M. auripes* and *M. ponticus* in both directions.

3rd cluster of morphologically close species

Merodon trebevicensis has a wide altitudinal range from sea level to approximately 2000 m a.s.l. *Merodon gallicus* has a smaller altitudinal range, from sea level up to 500 m. *Merodon hoplitis* is a mountain species (300-1450 m a.s.l.).

Taking into account only the factors with eigenvalues superior or equal to 1, four principal components were retained. These four factors together accounted for 90% of total variance. Environmental preferences differ significantly across the species in all four PCs using ANOVA (PC1: $F_{2,257} = 271.56$, $p < 0.00000$; PC2:

$F_{2,257} = 72.78$, $p < 0.00000$; PC3: $F_{2,257} = 9.91$, $p < 0.000071$; PC4: $F_{2,257} = 72.10$; $p < 0.00000$). PC1, with 52% of total variation, explained the gradient of annual precipitation and precipitation levels in the wettest and driest quarter and month. This axis separated *M. hoplitis* from *M. gallicus* and *M. trebevicensis*. PC2 showed temperature seasonality and annual temperature range. This axis was responsible for 21% of the total environmental variation (Fig. 6A). The temperature gradient of the coldest quarter and month and annual temperature levels were described with PC3 and explained 10% of total variation. This axis separated *M. gallicus* from the other two species. Precipitation seasonality was responsible for a small part of the total variation (PC4: 7%) and distinguished *M. gallicus* from *M. hoplitis* (Fig. 6B) (Table S1). Fisher's LSD test showed that all species pairs differed significantly among the four PCs ($p < 0.05$). Scatter plots showed the position of the investigated species in environmental space, and it was clear that the environmental niches differed partially and complexly, with a small overlap on all four axes (Fig. 6).

Of all three species from this cluster, *M. trebevicensis* had the widest adaptability. The very high value for PC3 reflects its wide distributional and altitudinal ranges. According to standard deviation values, *M. gallicus* had high adaptability for precipitation seasonality, and relatively high adaptability for annual and seasonal temperature variation (Table S2).

Potential distribution for *Merodon trebevicensis* revealed that the highest probability of occurrence (70-100%) was on the Dinaric and Carpatho-Balkan

Mountains, in Italy and on the mountains along the Black Sea, and probability from 50-70% was in the surrounding regions at lower altitudes. The potential distribution of *M. trebevicensis* (70-85%) overlaps with the distribution of *M. hoplitis*, while distribution of *M. gallicus* is completely separated (Fig. 4C).

The results of ENMTools showed that the niche overlap of the investigated species in the third cluster were between 0.346 (*M. hoplitis*-*M. trebevicensis*) and 0.543 (*M. gallicus*-*M. trebevicensis*) (Table S3). According to the identity test, the climate envelopes of all pairwise comparisons of *Merodon* species were highly significantly more different than expected as a random occurrence (Table S3). Results of the background test also supported ecological differentiation between species pairs; in most of the investigated pairs, niche similarity was greater than expected by chance, except between *M. hoplitis* and *M. gallicus*, where there was no significant difference ($p \geq 0.05$).

4th cluster of morphologically close species

Merodon loewi has the greatest altitudinal range of all species from the group, from 0 to above 2500 m a.s.l., while *M. ovaloides* and *M. turcicus* inhabit mountains above 1000 m (Fig. 2A). Point-based analysis of environmental variables showed that environmental preferences between these species differed in four dimensions (PC1-PC4). They together explained 92% of the total variation. ANOVA showed that overall differences across species were significant only in PC1 ($F_{2,311} = 17.92$, $p < 0.00000$). Fisher's LSD test showed that environmental preferences significantly differed only between *M. turcicus* and *M. loewi* in PC1 and PC2 ($p < 0.05$), and only these axes were included in the results' interpretation. PC1 was responsible for 36% of the total variation and depicted a gradient of annual mean temperature (Bio1), temperature in the coldest month (Bio6) and quarter (Bio11), as well as the mean temperature of the warmest quarter (Bio10) and the altitudinal range (Alt). PC2 is related to the precipitation level in the wettest quarter (Bio16) and month (Bio13), annual precipitation level (Bio12) and precipitation level in the coldest quarter (Bio19) (Fig. 7) (Table S1). PC2 explained 27% of the total variation. The environmental niche of *M. turcicus* partially differentiated from that of *M. loewi*, and had a much

Fig. 7. Distribution of species from cluster 4 in environmental space.

narrower range of temperature and precipitation than *M. loewi*.

The high values of standard deviation of PC1 and PC2 revealed the high adaptability of *M. loewi*, which is in concordance with its distributional and altitudinal range (Table S2). *Merodon ovaloides* had the lowest adaptability, while *M. turcicus* showed relatively high adaptation to annual temperature fluctuations (Table S2).

Based on niche projection, the highest probability of occurrence for *M. loewi* (70-100%) was along the Pindos mountains in Greece, and continued along Mt. Taygetos on the Peloponnese peninsula. The same probability of occurrence was in Turkey, along the Pontic Mountains and Mt. Taurus. 50-70% probability was on lower areas around these mountains, also on the Apennines and along the coastal zone of the Adriatic and Black seas. The potential distribution of *M. loewi* overlaps with the realized distributions of the two other species from this cluster (*M. turcicus* and *M. ovaloides*) in the range of 70-85%, which points to the similarities in ecological preferences among this species (Fig. 4D).

Cluster 4 had the highest value of niche overlap between species compared to the other investigated clusters, from 0.431 for *M. loewi*-*M. turcicus* to 0.550 for *M. ovaloides*-*M. turcicus*. The identity test showed that the pairs of species *M. loewi*-*M. turcicus* and *M. ovaloides*-*M. loewi* were significantly more different than expected by chance (Table S3), while there

were no significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$) between *M. ovaloides*-*M. turcicus*. For all pairs of *Merodon* species in this cluster, the niche similarity was more or less similar than expected by chance, but only in one direction (Table S3).

DISCUSSION

Recent research has clearly demonstrated the role of ecology in the speciation process [7,31,37,54,55]. It is clear that a species' range is influenced by its ecological niche [56], which is defined by the combination of environmental conditions and resources that are necessary for an organism to maintain a viable population [57].

This paper illustrates a trend of environmental divergence among related species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group. By observing the positions of environmental space of all investigated species, it was clear that species with a narrow range were restricted to a smaller part of the environmental space and constituted a subset of the realized niche of the widespread species. Low standard deviation values for endemic species reflect their narrow geographic distribution and very strict climatic adaptations, whereas large values for widely distributed species reflect their very broad adaptability. According to this, those widespread species (*M. auripes*, *M. loewi*, *M. ruficornis* and *M. trebevicensis*) could be considered as possible ancestors.

In all four comparisons our results showed that all species pairs differed in environmental niches, except *M. ovaloides* from *M. turcicus* and *M. loewi*. *Merodon turcicus* and *M. ovaloides* have narrow distributions connected to mountain peaks that are part of the potential distribution of *M. loewi* (Fig. 4D). The niche overlap between *M. ovaloides* and *M. turcicus* was the highest compared to the other investigated species, and presented the large degree of geographical overlap, while *M. ovaloides* and *M. loewi* do not differ on any PC axes. For all other species pairs, the identity test showed statistically significant niche diversification ($*p \leq 0.05$, $**p \leq 0.01$), and PCA showed separation on at least one environmental axis. All investigated species differed as regards temperature in the coldest quarter and month, while precipitation of driest quarter and month was responsible for the environmental separation of species from the second

and third clusters. Precipitation in the wettest quarter and month separated *M. ruficornis* from *M. abruzzensis* and *M. lamellatus* and all species from the third cluster. These factors represent the extreme or limiting environmental factors and they could be considered as partly responsible for speciation.

The axis related to altitude is always connected with temperature and depicts species replacement along altitude and temperature ranges (Cluster 1: PC1, Cluster 2: PC3, Cluster 4: PC1). Eight of the 12 species can be found at altitudes from 1000 to 2000 m a.s.l. The number of species above 2000 m gradually decreases and mostly encompasses endemic species. Their habitats are usually connected to high mountains in southern Europe, northern and eastern Turkey. Habitats in these areas with varied topography and lower latitude represent likely places for multiple glacial refugia [2,8-10,58,59]. Almost every mountain peak in this region has its own endemic species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group because these areas act like islands, which limits gene flow among them.

During the ice ages, many thermophilic organisms disappeared from most of their previous distribution areas and only survived in areas at lower latitudes with suitable climatic conditions. In Europe, these areas are located south of the transversal European high mountain systems, and represent the three most important refugial areas of the Mediterranean peninsulas [10,58,60,61]. Furthermore, the Maghreb and Asia Minor were also amongst the important refuges for thermophilic species during the glacial periods [8,62]. It can be assumed that species from the *Merodon ruficornis* group, like many other investigated taxa [4,10], have undergone many range contractions and expansions in and out of refugia in the south. During interglacials, some populations would survive in the high mountains, and during the cold periods (glaciation) they would descend to populate refugia at lower altitudes [61].

The mountains of the Alps and the Pyrenees acted as significant geographical barriers to the further spread of *M. gallicus*, while for *M. abruzzensis*, *M. alexandri* and *M. hoplitis* climate may explain the distributional constraints. These three species have significantly different climatic preferences restricted to a small part of the environmental space and low climatic adaptability. Although *M. gallicus* and *M. trebevicensis*

are extremely morphologically similar, differences in their environmental niches are statistically significant. *Merodon gallicus* inhabits drier and warmer areas with less seasonal temperature variability, which is not suitable for morphologically related species. These environmental factors, in combination with the geological history of the Maritime Alps (France) could explain the present-day distribution of *M. gallicus* [63-65]. *Merodon hoplitis* is distributed along the coastline of Montenegro and Croatia, as the consequence of newly acquired specific climatic conditions (higher humidity and milder temperatures during the year) that are provided in Dinaric microrefugia near the coastal zone [66]. Also, the distribution of *M. alexandri* is limited by specific environmental factors. This species has very low adaptability to all environmental factors represented by the PCs. It is a lowland species that inhabits Ukraine and the Russian steppes, which are characterized by extreme continental conditions.

Species diversity in the *Merodon ruficornis* group is high in comparison with other groups of this genus. Twelve of 18 (66.5%) species are endemic and have very local distribution connected with only a few mountain peaks on the Balkan Peninsula, Turkey and in the Caucasus region [21]. These areas were influenced by diverse climatic and other geographic conditions in the past. This can explain a large number of local endemic insect species in the main refugia of the Western Palearctic, which are also the main hotspots for many insect species [4,60].

Future field investigations are necessary to enlarge the sampled material, particularly for rare species, as well as to complement this diverse group with new members, probably endemics from isolated mountain peaks. As glacial and interglacial periods have left distinctive marks on the genomes of many species, including those from the *Merodon ruficornis* group, further investigations should utilize recent advances in molecular analysis in order to improve our understanding of the phylogenetic relationships.

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia OI173002 and III43002 and the Provincial Secretariat for Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Genetic Resources of Agroecosystems in Vojvodina and Sustainable Agriculture). We are grateful to Jennifer and Victoria

Wickens from the University of Reading, UK for English revision during the writing process.

Authors' contribution: JA, MM and LL wrote the paper; AV, SR, JA, MM and LL collected new specimens; AV and SR identified the specimens; AJ, MM and LL performed PCA analysis, MM performed SDM analysis; DM performed ENMtool analysis; JA and MM prepared the figures; all authors contributed to manuscript with comments and revision.

Conflict of interest disclosure: We certify that we have no any actual or potential conflict of interest including any financial, personal or other relationships with other people or organizations within three years of beginning the submitted work that could inappropriately influence, or be perceived to influence, their work.

REFERENCES

1. Coope GR. The Response of Insect Faunas to Glacial-Interglacial Climatic Fluctuations. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 1994;344(1307):19-26.
2. Hewitt GM. Speciation, hybrid zones and phylogeography-or seeing genes in space and time. *Mol Ecol.* 2001;10(3):537-49.
3. Konstantinov AS, Korotyaev BA, Volkovitsh MG. Insect biodiversity in the Palearctic Region. In: Foottit RG, Adler PH, editors. *Insect biodiversity: science and society.* Oxford, UK: Wiley-Blackwell; 2009. p. 107-62.
4. Dapporto L. Speciation in Mediterranean refugia and postglacial expansion of *Zerynthia polyxena* (Lepidoptera, Papilionidae). *J Zool Syst Evol Res.* 2010;48(3):229-37.
5. Ujvárosi L, Bálint M, Schmitt T, Mészáros N, Ujvárosi T, Popescu O. Divergence and speciation in the Carpathians area: patterns of morphological and genetic diversity of the crane fly *Pedicia occulta* (Diptera: Pediciidae). *J North Am Benthol Soc.* 2010;29(3):1075-88.
6. Nicholls JA, Preuss S, Hayward A, Melika G, Csóka GY, Nieves-Aldrey J, Askew RR, Tavakoli M, Schönrogge K, Stone GN. Concordant phylogeography and cryptic speciation in two Western Palearctic oak gall parasitoid species complexes. *Mol Ecol.* 2010;19(3):592-609.
7. Zhu G, Liu G, Bu W, Lis JA. Geographic distribution and niche divergence of two stinkbugs, *Parastrachia japonensis* and *Parastrachia nagaensis*. *J Insect Sci.* 2013;13(1):102.
8. Seddon JM, Santucci F, Reeve N, Hewitt GM. Caucasus Mountains divide postulated postglacial colonization routes in the white-breasted hedgehog, *Erinaceus concolor*. *J Evolution Biol.* 2002;15(3):463-7.
9. Habel JC, Drees C, Schmitt T, Assmann T. Refugial areas and postglacial colonisations in the Western Palearctic. In: Habel JC, Assmann T, editors. *Relict Species - Phylogeography and Conservation Biology.* Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag; 2010. p. 189-98.
10. Hewitt GM. Post-glacial re-colonization of European biota. *Biol J Linn Soc.* 1999;68(1-2):87-112.
11. Vujić A, Radenković S, Likov L, Trifunov S, Nikolić T. Three new species of the *Merodon nigratarsis* group (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the Middle East. *Zootaxa.* 2013;3640(2):442-64.

12. Vujić A, Radenković S, Ačanski J, Grković A, Taylor M, Şenol SG, Hayat R. Revision of the species of the *Merodon nanus* group (Diptera: Syrphidae) including three new species. *Zootaxa*. 2015;4006(3):439-62.
13. Ricarte A, Marcos-García MA, Rotheray GE. The early stages and life histories of three *Eumerus* and two *Merodon* species (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the Mediterranean region. *Entomol Fennica*. 2008;19(2):129-41.
14. Radenković S, Vujić A, Ståhls G, Pérez-Bañón C, Rojo S, Petanidou T, Šimić S. Three new cryptic species of the genus *Merodon* Meigen (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the island of Lesbos (Greece). *Zootaxa*. 2011;2735:35-56.
15. Andrić A, Šikoparija B, Obreht D, Djan M, Preradović J, Radenković S, Pérez-Bañón S, Vujić A. DNA barcoding applied: identifying the larva of *Merodon avidus* (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Acta Ent Mus Nat Pra*. 2014;54(2):741-57.
16. Speight MCD. Syrph the Net, the database of European Syrphidae. Vol. 83, Species accounts of European Syrphidae (Diptera), 2015. Dublin: Syrph the Net publications; 2015. 295 p.
17. Ståhls G, Vujić A, Pérez-Bañón C, Radenković S, Rojo S, Petanidou T. COI barcodes for identification of *Merodon* hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) of Lesbos Island, Greece. *Mol Ecol Resour*. 2009;9(6):1431-38.
18. Vujić A, Marcos-García MÁ, Sarıbiyık S, Ricarte A. New data on the *Merodon* Meigen 1803 fauna (Diptera: Syrphidae) of Turkey including description of a new species and changes in the nomenclatural status of several taxa. *Ann Soc Entomol Fr*. 2011;47(1-2):78-88.
19. Radenković S, Vujić A, Šimić S. On the identity and synonymy of two species from *Merodon ruficornis* Meigen group (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Acta entomol Serb*. 2002;7(1/2):51-7.
20. Vujić A, Pérez-Bañón C, Radenković S, Ståhls G, Rojo S, Petanidou T, Šimić S. Two new species of the genus *Merodon* Meigen 1803 (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the island of Lesbos (Greece), in the eastern Mediterranean. *Ann Soc Entomol Fr*. 2007;43(3):319-26.
21. Vujić A, Radenković S, Ståhls G, Ačanski J, Stefanović A, Veselić S, Andrić A, Hayat R. Systematics and taxonomy of the *ruficornis* group of genus *Merodon* Meigen (Diptera: Syrphidae). *Syst Entomol*. 2012;37(3):578-602.
22. Milankov V, Ståhls G, Vujić A. Molecular diversity of populations of the *Merodon ruficornis* group (Diptera, Syrphidae) on the Balkan Peninsula. *J Zool Syst Evol Res*. 2008;46(2):143-152.
23. Popov GV. *Merodon alexandri* spec. nov. – a new species of hoverfly (Diptera: Syrphidae) from the northern Black Sea Region. *Studia Dipt*. 2010;16:133-51.
24. Wiens JJ, Graham CH. Niche conservatism: integrating evolution, ecology, and conservation biology. *Annu Rev Ecol Syst*. 2005;36:519-39.
25. Raxworthy C, Ingram C, Rabibisoa N, Pearson R. Applications of ecological niche modeling for species delimitation: a review and empirical evaluation using day geckos (*Phelsuma*) from Madagascar. *Syst Biol*. 2007;56(6):907-23.
26. Schuller D. Evidence for ecological speciation and its alternative. *Science*. 2009;323(5915):737-741.
27. McCormack JE, Zellmer AJ, Knowles LL. Does niche divergence accompany allopatric divergence in *Aphelocoma* jays as predicted under ecological speciation?: insights from tests with niche models. *Evolution*. 2010;64(5):1231-44.
28. Hutchinson GE. Concluding remarks. *Cold Spring Harb Symp Quant Biol*. 1957;22:415-427.
29. Graham CH, Ron SR, Santos JC, Schneider CJ, Moritz C. Integrating phylogenetics and environmental niche models to explore speciation mechanisms in dendrobatid frogs. *Evolution*. 2004;58(8):1781-93.
30. Rissler LJ, Apodaca JJ. Adding more ecology into species delimitation: ecological niche models and phylogeography help define cryptic species in the black salamander (*Aneides flavipunctatus*). *Syst Biol*. 2007;56(6):924-42.
31. Stockman AK, Bond JE. Delimiting cohesion species: extreme population structuring and the role of ecological interchangeability. *Mol Ecol*. 2007;16(16):3374-92.
32. Bond JE, Stockman AK. An integrative method for delimiting cohesion species: finding the population-species interface in a group of Californian trapdoor spiders with extreme genetic divergence and geographic structuring. *Syst Biol*. 2008;57(4):628-46.
33. Nosil P, Luke JH, Ole S. Ecological explanations for (incomplete) speciation. *Trends Ecol Evol*. 2009;24(3):145-56.
34. Medley KA. Niche shifts during the global invasion of the Asian tiger mosquito, *Aedes albopictus* Skuse (Culicidae), revealed by reciprocal distribution models. *Global Ecol Biogeogr*. 2010;19(1):122-33.
35. Sánchez-Fernández D, Lobo JM, Abellán P, Millán A. Environmental niche divergence between genetically distant lineages of an endangered water beetle. *Biol J Linn Soc*. 2011;103(4):891-903.
36. Wooten JA, Gibbs HL. Niche divergence and lineage diversification among closely related *Sistrurus* rattlesnakes. *J Evolution Biol*. 2012;25(2):317-28.
37. Zhou WW, Wen Y, Fu J, Xu YB, Jin JQ, Ding L, Min MS, Che J, Zhang YP. Speciation in the *Rana chensinensis* species complex and its relationship to the uplift of the Qinghai-Tibetan Plateau. *Mol Ecol*. 2012;21(4):960-73.
38. Petersen MJ. Evidence of a climatic niche shift following North American introductions of two crane flies (Diptera; genus *Tipula*). *Biol Invasions*. 2013;15(4):885-97.
39. Phillips SJ, Anderson RP, Schapire RE. Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. *Ecol Model*. 2006;190(3):231-59.
40. Guisan A, Thuiller W. Predicting species distribution: offering more than simple habitat models. *Ecol Lett*. 2005;8(9):993-1009.
41. Jeschke JM, Strayer DL. Usefulness of bioclimatic models for studying climate change and invasive species. In: Ostfeld RS, Schlesinger WH, editors. *The year in ecology and conservation 2008*. Boston, Mass.: Blackwell Pub; 2008. p. 1-24. (*Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*; vol. 1134)
42. Elith J, Graham CH. Do they? How do they? Why do they differ? On finding reasons for differing performances of species distribution models. *Ecography*. 2009;32(1):66-77.
43. Hijmans RJ, Cameron SE, Parra JL, Jones PG, Jarvis A. The WorldClim Interpolated Global Terrestrial Climate Surfaces. [Internet]. Berkeley, CA, USA: University of Berkeley; 2005. [cited 2014 Jan 27]. Available from: <http://www.worldclim.org/current>

44. Phillips SJ, Dudik M, Schapire RE. A maximum entropy approach to species distribution modeling. In Brodley CE, editor. Proceedings: 21st International Conference on Machine Learning; 2004 Jul 4-8; Banff, Alberta, Canada. New York: ACM; 2004. p. 655-62.
45. Merow C, Smith MJ, Silander JA. A practical guide to MaxEnt for modeling species' distributions: what it does, and why inputs and settings matter. *Ecography*. 2013;36(10):1058-69.
46. Ortega-Huerta MA, Peterson AT. Modeling ecological niches and predicting geographic distributions: a test of six presence-only methods. *Rev Mex Biodivers*. 2008;79(1):205-16.
47. Peterson AT, Papes M, Eaton M. Transferability and model evaluation in ecological niche modeling: a comparison of GARP and Maxent. *Ecography*. 2007;30(4):550-60.
48. Phillips SJ, Dudik M. Modeling of species distributions with Maxent: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation. *Ecography*. 2008;31(2):161-75.
49. Jaynes ET. Information theory and statistical mechanics. *Phys. Rev*. 1957;106(4):620-30.
50. Araújo MB, Pearson RG, Thuiller W, Erhard M. Validation of species-climate impact models under climate change. *Global Change Biol*. 2005;11(9):1504-13.
51. Warren DL, Glor RE, Turelli M. Environmental niche equivalency versus conservatism: quantitative approaches to niche evolution. *Evolution*. 2008;62(11):2868-83.
52. Warren DL, Glor RE, Turelli M. ENMTools: a toolbox for comparative studies of environmental niche models. *Ecography*. 2010;33(3):607-11.
53. Schoener T.W. The Anolis lizards of Bimini: resource partitioning in a complex fauna. *Ecology*. 1968;49(4):704-26.
54. Peterson AT. Ecological niche conservatism: a time-structured review of evidence. *J Biogeogr*. 2011;38(5):817-27.
55. Nosal P. Ecological speciation. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2012. 280 p.
56. Peterson AT, Hold RD. Niche differentiation in Mexican birds: using point occurrences to detect ecological innovation. *Ecol Lett*. 2003;6(8):774-82.
57. MacArthur, RH. Geographical ecology: patterns in the distribution of species. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press; 1984. 269 p.
58. Taberlet P, Fumagalli L, Wust-Saucy A, Cosson J. Comparative phylogeography and postglacial colonization routes in Europe. *Mol Ecol*. 1998;7(4):453-64.
59. Hewitt GM. Genetic consequences of climatic oscillations in the Quaternary. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*. 2004;359(1442):183-95.
60. Balletto E, Casale A. Mediterranean Insect conservation. In: Collins NM, Thomas JA, editors. The conservation of insects and their habitats. London: Academic Press; 1991. p. 121-42.
61. Hewitt GM. Some genetic consequences of ice ages, and their role, in divergence and speciation. *Biol J Linn Soc*. 1996;58(3):247-76.
62. Habel JC, Meyer M, El Mousadik A, Schmitt T. Africa goes Europe: The complete phylogeography of the marbled white butterfly species complex *Melanargia galathea/M. lachesis* (Lepidoptera: Satyridae). *Org Divers Evol*. 2008;8(2):121-9.
63. Malaroda R, Carraro F, Dal Piaz GB, Franceschetti B, Sturani C, Zanella E. Carta Geologica del Massiccio dell'Argentera alla scala 1:50.000 e note illustrative. *Memorie S G I*. 1970;9:557-663.
64. Federici PR, Spagnolo M. Morphometric analysis on the size, shape and areal distribution of glacial cirques in the Maritime Alps (Western French Italian Alps). *Geogr Ann A*. 2004;86(3):235-48.
65. Buoncristiani JF, Campy M. Quaternary Glaciations in the French Alps and Jura. In: Ehlers J, Gibbard PL, editors. Quaternary Glaciations: Extent and Chronology, Part 1: Europe. Amsterdam: Elsevier; 2004. p. 117-26.
66. Hughes PD, Woodward JC, Gibbard PL. Quaternary glacial history of the Mediterranean mountains. *Prog Phys Geog*. 2006;30(3):334-64.

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Principal component analysis of 19 Bioclim and altitude variable associated with occurrence points of species from *Merodon ruficornis* group. Significant factor loadings are printed in bold. The table can be assessed on: <http://serbiosoc.org.rs/sup/Supps1s3/TableS1.xlsx>

Table S2. Climatic adaptability indicated by the standard deviation of the mean factor scores for each species from *Merodon ruficornis* group. The table can be assessed on: <http://serbiosoc.org.rs/sup/Supps1s3/TableS2.xlsx>

Table S3. Ecological niche comparisons for species of *Merodon ruficornis* group. Niche overlap values are presented for the comparisons of niche identity and similarity of species A with species B. *, **The ecological niches are significantly (*p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01) more similar or different than expected by chance; MD – more different; MS – more similar; LS – less similar; NS – not significant. The table can be assessed on: <http://serbiosoc.org.rs/sup/Supps1s3/TableS3.xlsx>